

FINANCIAL LITERACY AND DECISION-MAKING SKILLS FOR AN IMPROVED TEACHER'S FINANCIAL WELL-BEING AND PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES

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ABSTRACT

Amid the pandemic brought by COVID-19, it is not only the schools, curriculum and the learners who have undergo changes in the transition of education from traditional face-to-face learning to distance learning modality. Teachers are also moving forward in order to adopt in the said changes. Unfortunately, many teachers are experiencing financial stress due to their financial matters because they are still unable to manage their finances properly and experiencing problems when it comes to budgeting and loan management. This study attempted to determine the impact of financial literacy and decision-making skills in improving the financial well-being and professional qualities of public school teachers. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire. There were 177 teacher-respondents teaching in fifteen schools in Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon, conducted last April 2021. Based on the result, the personal characteristics of the respondents include age, gender, civil status, education and ability, work status, years in service and net take home pay indicated that majority were above 31-40 years old and females. Most of them were married, having bachelor's degree, Teacher I, have a net take home pay of P15,000 – P 24,000 and rendered 1-10 years in service. Teachers' financial literacy and the decision-making skills are proven to be practiced. Furthermore, financial well-being and professional qualities were also being practiced. The researcher recommends that the teachers should be careful in managing their finances. They have to keep themselves aware about the proper ways of spending their money and the importance of savings and investments. They should also bear in mind that despite all the worries and stress that they are experiencing, they should keep themselves in doing their best in their profession.

Keywords: Decision Making, Financial Literacy, Financial Well-Being